

Discourse Strategies in the Representing of Islam on Google News Indonesia: A Critical Study of Digital Media Framing

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Abstract

Background: Research on religious discourse in the media has generally focused on print media or social media. Few investigations have examined how representations of Islam are constructed through news headlines, metadata, and digital discourse strategies that intersect with religious ideologies and majority–minority relations.

Objective: This research examines the patterns of discourse on the reporting of Islam in Google News Indonesia, for three reasons: (1) the need to understand the various strategies of discourse on Islam in a digital news aggregation platform; (2) the need to know the forms of Islamic representation; and (3) the need to explain social and ideological functions of the Islamic discourse as shaped by digital mediation.

Methodology: Data were compiled from screenshots and documentation of religious news content. Norman Fairclough's and Teun A. van Dijk's models of critical discourse analysis and Robert Entman's semiotic and framing approaches were used for analysis.

Results: This study found that the discourse strategies in Islamic news on Google News Indonesia are personalization, legitimization, emotive narration, and prescriptive-normative discourse. These strategies are manifested not only in the textual content but also in unique visual and structural elements of Google News Indonesia —particularly its titles, summaries, and metadata—that

characterize the aggregator's display system. Through these digital features, discourse strategies contribute to shaping public opinion, guiding readers' interpretive frames, and reinforcing social and moral values. Depicting Islam in varied expressions—spiritual, normative, social, practical, historical, and cultural—illustrates the adaptable nature of Islam as a value system that can be made relevant for different contexts.

Conclusion: Islamic meta-language on Google News Indonesia is not only supernatural al but also humanistic and situational, qualifying as an instrument for sociological enlightenment and an ideology of progress and inclusivism. The findings underline that the algorithmic and aggregative structure of Google News Indonesia actively mediates Islamic discourse, highlighting how digital platforms participate in constructing modern religious representations.

Unique Contribution: This study uniquely shows that Islamic discourse in Google News Indonesia is framed not as a purely transcendental narrative, but as a humanizing and contextual discourse shaped by key strategies—personalization, legitimization, emotive narration, and prescriptive-normative appeals. These strategies make Islam appear compassionate, approachable, and socially engaged, reflecting its relevance to everyday life. The link between these discourse forms and Google News Indonesia digital architecture highlights how algorithmic mediation amplifies inclusive and value-oriented representations of Islam as a modern agent of social change.

Key Recommendation: Journalists in particular should shift from ratio oriented negative stories about Islam to explain and balance the context of Islam for inclusive media practice and social change, while on future research.

Keywords: discourse strategies; Islamic representation; Google News Indonesia; Critical Discourse Analysis; digital media framing; social and ideological functions

Introduction

The representation of Islam in digital media has become an important field of inquiry. As a major information hub, Google News Indonesia influences how religious issues reach the public. Because Islamic news significantly shapes public opinion (Fuazy & Jannah, 2021), examining objectivity, bias, and discursive strategies is essential. Research over the past two decades shows that Muslims are often framed as cultural outsiders or security threats through fear-based narratives and “we/they” binaries. In Western contexts, Islam is frequently linked to terrorism, migration, or incompatibility with Western values (Silva, 2020). Yet few studies connect discursive media strategies to deeper religious ideologies or to internal majority–minority dynamics within Islam.

Google News Indonesia It is grounded in a more basic question: how does the discursive formation in news aggregator mediate and naturalize the portrayal of Islam in the digital public sphere? A search-engine-driven content hub, Google News not only influences how religious news is displayed but also how it is chosen, ranked, and interpreted. This poses essential questions: What kind of discursive strategies do they employ to highlight Islam in headlines and news reports? Are the images produced a product of the internal diversity of Muslim communities, or do they merely reproduce dominant ideologies, political predispositions and specific stereotypes?

The contributions of the study are twofold. In theoretical terms, it contributes to our knowledge of religious representation in the digital media, with a focus on the under-theorised impact of news aggregators like Google News, and builds upon the body of Islamic studies literature in the domain

of on digital communication and online media discourse. Theoretically, the results offer novel reflections in professional coverage of religion to journalist and editorial departments in promoting sensitivity to bias and framing in religious coverage and empowering media literacy. In this manner, the public is better prepared to engage critically and self-reflexively with the portrayals of Islam in the digital realm.

Literature Review

Critical Discourse Analysis

This examination of discourse strategies in Islam reporting on Google News Indonesia is rooted in a critical theoretical approach. Fairclough (2013) treats discourse as more than text but as a social practice. From this vantage point, attention to Islam in the media can be seen as a site at which language works to naturalize certain values. Van Dijk (2006) elaborates on this with the socio-cognitive approach and claims that ideology works through the collective mental schemas, under the control of macro-discourse elites, such as journalists, or mainstream media. Althusser (2024) even adds an ideological dimension to this approach by the employment of ideology state apparatuses (ISA).

Strategies and Forms of Representation

The study of discourse strategies in news reporting—particularly concerning the representation of Islam on Google News Indonesia. This research draws on classical foundations of critical discourse studies, such as Van Dijk (2006) work on ideology and social cognition, Van Leeuwen (2009) analysis of legitimation and authority, Fairclough (2023) exploration of institutionalization and interdiscursivity, Althusser (2024) theorization of moral-ideological interpellation. Nonetheless, these classical theories can be enriched by contemporary perspectives that highlight the dynamics of the digital sphere. A model with multiple dimensions also opens the way for a more nuanced explanation of the social and ideological roles of the media in constructing public perceptions of Islam in the digital age.

At the same time, Hall et al. (2024) argue that representation is not resulting speech act; that is, it is not a passive reflection of society (reality) but, rather, an active production of meaning through the mediation of socially- sanctioned language, images, and signs. From the framing point of view, Entman (1993) identifies the way in which the media selects certain features to emphasize them and connect them to moral evaluation and remedies. Ultimately, the notion of the Muslim Public Sphere (Eickelman, 2003) how contemporary media, like Google News Indonesia, facilitates the construction of Islamic identities and discourses.

Ideological and Social Functions

The social and ideological role of media discourse intersect to shape Islam in the public domain. From a social standpoint, religion as a social construction Berger and Luckmann (2016) works as an apparatus. This metaphor carries the additional connotations of religion as a system of cultural meaning advanced by Geertz (2017) religion, Islam not excluded, now occurs not just in private space but plays an active role in the public sphere, including digital mass media Casanova (1994). On the other hand, the ideological function can be explained through Van Dijk (2006) “ideology in discourse” saying that media create “us” versus “them” position in language.

Methodology

This qualitative study uses CDA based on Fairclough and Van Dijk to uncover meanings, ideologies, and power relations in Google News Indonesia. The dataset covers Islamic news from May–July 2025. Sources include mainstream outlets (e.g., detikcom, CNBC Indonesia) and religious institutions (e.g., Rumah Zakat, Muhammadiyah). About two-thirds of items came from mainstream media.

Data collection involved searching “Islam” on Google News Indonesia, documenting headlines, archiving articles, and recording metadata (category, labels, keywords, algorithmic indicators). Thirty-one articles met the criteria relevant articles were analyzed.

Analysis proceeded through:

- (1) micro-textual examination (lexis, syntax, metaphor);
- (2) discursive practice analysis (production, reproduction, institutional patterns);
- (3) macro-social analysis (ideology, power relations);
- (4) framing analysis (problem definition, causality, moral evaluation, proposed solutions).

Findings across levels were synthesized to identify dominant patterns and ideological implications of Islamic representation on Google News Indonesia.

Results and Discussion

Islamic news on Google News Indonesia employs strategies involving authority, morality, spirituality, ritual, and culture. Authorization, legitimation, moral evaluation, and interpellation (Althusser, 2024) shape how Islamic actors and events are represented. Ritual and textual orientations reflect broader discursive practices (Fairclough, 2023).

Discourse Strategies in Islamic News on Google News Indonesia

The discourse strategies in digital religious texts reveal dimensions of authority, morality, spirituality, ritual, and culture. Authority and legitimacy are understood through authorization, legitimation (Van Leeuwen, 2009), and ideological strategies (Van Dijk, 2006). Moral and normative aspects are grasped through moral evaluation (Van Leeuwen, 2009) and interpellation (Althusser, 2024). Ritual procedures and textual orientation reflect rationalization (Van Leeuwen, 2009) and discursive practice dimensions (Fairclough, 2023).

Table 1. Discourse Strategies in Islamic News on Google News Indonesia

No	News Headline	Discourse Strategy	Function Opinion Formation	in Representation Note
1	5 Ciri-ciri Orang yang Mendapatkan Malam Lailatul Qadar (CNBC Indonesia) https://search.app/SXK1S 5 Characteristics of	<i>Personalization & Legitimization</i>	<i>Cultivating personal spiritual aspiration</i>	<i>Islam as personal spirituality</i>

	<i>People Who Attain the Night of Lailatul Qadar</i>			
2	Ramadhan Segera (Althusser) Berakhir, Kenali Tanda Jika Puasa Kita Diterima (Rumah Zakat) https://search.app/d6epw <i>Ramadan is Ending Soon, Recognize the Signs that Our Fasting is Accepted</i>	(Althusser) <i>Interpellation & Moral Imperative</i>	<i>Directing readers toward self-evaluation</i>	<i>Islam as an evaluative and reflective religion</i>
3	Hukum Puasa 6 Hari pada Bulan Syawal https://search.app/YDeeK (detikcom) <i>The Ruling of Fasting Six Days in the Month of Shawwal</i>	Authoritative Voice Ulama (Van Leeuwen)	<i>Encouraging compliance with Islamic jurisprudence</i>	<i>Islam as a legal (sharia) system</i>
4	7 Khutbah Jumat Bulan Syawal yang Menyentuh Hati (detikcom) https://search.app/wvkSz <i>7 Touching Friday Sermons in the Month of Shawwal</i>	Emotive Appeal & Narrative Structure (Van Leeuwen)	<i>Creating a religious atmosphere post-Ramadan</i>	<i>Islam as a religion sustaining continuity of worship</i>
5	13 Cara Sederhana agar Tetap Bersyukur dalam Hidup (VIVA Banyuwangi) https://serach.app/cBAKm <i>13 Simple Ways to Remain Grateful in Life</i>	<i>Didactic & Imperative Strategy</i>	<i>Internalizing Islamic values in daily life</i>	<i>Islam as a positive lifestyle</i>
6	7 Contoh Ceramah Halal Bihalal Singkat yang Penuh Pesan Eratkan Silaturahmi (detikcom) https://search.app/Dm7Rr <i>7 Examples of Short Halal Bihalal Sermons with Strong Messages to Strengthen Brotherhood</i>	<i>Interactive & Functional</i>	<i>Promoting Islamic social values</i>	<i>Islam as a religion of social harmony</i>
7	50 Kata-kata Bijak Umar bin Khattab, Bisa Jadi Penyemangat Hidup (detikcom) https://rearch.app/2N7rf	<i>Intertextuality of Historical Figures</i>	<i>Establishing authority of Islamic moral values</i>	<i>Islam represented through the Prophet's companions</i>

	<i>50 Wise Sayings of Umar ibn Khattab, A Source of Life Motivation</i>			
8	6 Teks Khutbah Jumat Bulan Syawal Lengkap dengan Doa (detikcom) https://search.app/Ka1tp <i>6 Friday Sermon Texts in Shawwal Complete with Prayers</i>	Textual Support & Ritual Frame (Van Leeuwen)	<i>Providing practical tools for preaching</i>	<i>Islam as a ritualistic and practical religion</i>
9	Menengok Tradisi Memasak Bubur Asyura di Nusantara (CNN Indonesia) https://search.app/9bT3z <i>Revisiting the Tradition of Cooking Asyura Porridge in the Archipelago</i>	Cultural Representation & Local Wisdom (Wodak)	<i>Reinforcing local Islamic cultural identity</i>	<i>Islam as a living community tradition</i>
10	Doa Pagi Hari agar Rezeki Lancar dan Hati Tenang (CNN Indonesia) https://search.app/Avg8P <i>Morning Prayer for Smooth Livelihood and Peace of Mind</i>	Transaksional Piety (Van Leeuwen)	<i>spiritual Building spiritual hope and motivation</i>	<i>Islam as a personal solution in modern life</i>
11	Lengkap dengan Artinya! Ini Doa Shahih Setelah Sholat Dhuha (Rumah Zakat) https://search.app/BdDDt <i>Complete with Its Meaning! The Authentic Prayer after Duha</i>	Normative Instruction & Authentication (Van Leeuwen)	<i>Strengthening authentic religious practices in daily life</i>	<i>Islam as an authentic standardized teaching</i>
12	Ketahui! Begini Cara Menjawab Azan dengan Benar (Rumah Zakat) https://search.app/iuynQ <i>Know This! How to Properly Respond to the Call to Prayer</i>	Preskriptif & Normatif (Van Leeuwen) <i>Prescriptive & Normative</i>	<i>Safeguarding the validity of religious practices</i>	<i>Islam as a precise and correct teaching</i>

Findings show that discourse strategies in digital reporting on Islam are contextual rather than uniform. Personalization, legitimation, interpellation, and moral claims internalize religious values and prompt readers' self-reflection. Prescriptive norms frame Islam as law and guidance.

Emotionalisation, religious narration, didactic forms, and interactive functions function as key attractions. Intertextual references, ritual framing, and cultural-local wisdom representations present Islam through authority figures, worship practices, and sociocultural traditions, echoing (Alam et al., 2026). Transactional piety shows how prayer connects to daily life. Together, these strategies construct a composite and multidimensional digital image of Islam.

Categories of Islamic Representation in News Coverage

Islamic depiction in digital media is not merely factual but a social construct shaped by ideology and interests. Through selective headlines, wording, naming, and framing, Islam appears in multiple modes: as peace, tolerance, and da'wah, or as linked to conflict, crime, or radicalism. These variations show that representations of Islam are never neutral.

Table 2. Islamic Representation in News Coverage

No.	Judul Berita & Sumber	Representasi Keislaman	Fungsi	Diskursus
13	Anak Adalah Amanah, Bukan Beban: Renungan Islami di Hari Anak Nasional 2025 (Rumah Zakat, https://search.app/gAK9D) <i>Children Are a Trust, Not a Burden: An Islamic Reflection on National Children's Day 2025</i>	<i>Religious values: children as God's trust; Islamic moral values in a national momentum</i>	<i>Internalizati on of tawhid and trust values</i>	<i>Islam positioned as a worldview integrated with national celebration</i>
14	Cara Melakukan Shalat Taubat Lengkap Beserta Doanya (Rumah Zakat, https://search.app/FvjSd) <i>How to Perform the Complete Prayer of Repentance and Its Supplication</i>	<i>Islamic ritual practice; religious education through repentance prayer guidance</i>	<i>Educational and spiritual; guiding the community toward repentance</i>	<i>Islam as a practical religion present in every stage of life</i>
15	Menjadi Mukhlis di Tengah Godaan Munafik: Tafsir Al-Baqarah 204–207 (Muhammadiyah, https://search.app/hEPLw) <i>Becoming a Mukhlis Amid the Temptations of Hypocrisy: Tafsir of Al-Baqarah 204–207</i>	<i>Qur'anic exegesis; moral dichotomy of sincere believer vs hypocrite</i>	<i>Theological reflection on social and individual conditions</i>	<i>Islam as a moral guide in confronting modern spiritual crises</i>
16	Sedekah Diam-Diam: Amalan Ikhlas dengan Balasan Terbaik (Rumah	<i>Sincere deeds; transcendental</i>	<i>Encouraging virtuous practice and</i>	<i>Islam as an internalization of</i>

	Zakat, https://search.app/c5a4t <i>Secret Charity: A Sincere Deed with the Best Reward</i>	<i>motivation in charity</i>	<i>avoiding ostentation</i>	<i>moral and spiritual values</i>
17	Kementerian Agama Luncurkan Kurikulum Berbasis Cinta (Kementerian Agama RI, https://search.app/6j55W) <i>Ministry of Religious Affairs Launches Love-Based Curriculum</i>	<i>Humanistic Islam; institutionalization of Islamic values in education</i>	<i>Balancing religiosity and psychology in education</i>	<i>Islam as the foundation of national character education</i>
18	Kafilah MTQ Kapanewon Galur Siap Berlagu! (Kemenag Kulon Progo, https://search.app/5GAzr) <i>Galur Subdistrict MTQ Delegation Ready to Compete!</i>	<i>Islamic tradition (MTQ) as preservation of Qur'anic culture</i>	<i>Manifestation of faith and achievement</i>	<i>Islam as cultural strength and collective identity of the ummah</i>
19	Pesan Menag pada Wisudawan Santri Tahfiz 30 Juz: Jadilah Al-Quran Berjalan (Kementerian Agama RI, https://search.app/Z3wDh) <i>Minister's Message to Graduating Santri of 30-Juz Memorization: Be a Living Qur'an</i>	<i>Qur'an internalization; ideal Muslim figure (Qur'anic generation)</i>	<i>Character education; nurturing future scholars</i>	<i>Islam as ethos of life and social model</i>
20	Kemenag Kumpulkan Ratusan Pegiat Kerukunan, Awal Agustus 2025 (Kemenag RI, https://search.app/SkHa3) <i>Ministry of Religious Affairs Gathers Hundreds of Harmony Activists, Early August 2025</i>	<i>Islam as Rahmatan lil 'Alamin; religious moderation</i>	<i>Interfaith dialogue; maintaining national harmony</i>	<i>Islam as social cohesion in a multicultural society</i>

The results in Table 2 suggest that media representations of Islam in news discourse are multifaceted, covering the ritualistic, moral, cultural and socio-political. On the individual level, reports on inter alia shalat taubat (14), Qur'anic exegesis (15) and secret charity (16) emphasise the internalization of moral and spiritual values, working towards the popular positioning Islam as at once a practical religion and a guide for individual conduct in modern moral crises. On the level

of Family and Community, the motif of children as a divine deposit (13), and the message of the Minister of Religious Affairs to Qur'an graduates (19) frame Islam as the moral basis and social blueprint for the next generation. The existence of Islam as a part of public policy can be seen from the love-based curriculum (17) that integrates religion morality and psychology of education and from the Qur'an recitation competition (18) affirming that Islam is a collective cultural identity. Secondly, peace building programs of the Ministry of Religious Affairs (20) present Islam as *rahmatan lil 'alamin* in the perspective of pluralism and nationhood. More generally, Islam is pictured as a perspective, moral guideline, cultural heritage, educational tool, and social binder thus wielding a great deal of sociopragmatic influence in achieving accord across individuals as well as among the society.

Activities and functions of ideology in Islamic discourse portrayed at Google News media

Islamic discourse in online media, especially on Google News, is not just an informational channel but rather serves important social and ideological functions. Discursively, this rhetoric constructs public perceptions of who is positioned as aligned with opposed to the nation's way of life through stories of tolerance, conflict, da'wah, and criminality. AS a matter of SD5 linguistic representation Islamic discourse in the mass media is never neutral; it is always carrying constructed meanings, which are tied to particular interests, support or discredit the images of certain groups, and mediate power relations among the state, society, and religious institutes. These data are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Social and Ideological Functions of Islamic Discourse

No.	News Title	Fungsi Sosial	Ideological Function
21	Muhammadiyah dan Baznas Jalin Kolaborasi Strategis Majukan Pendidikan Islam (<u>Muhammadiyah</u>) <i>Muhammadiyah and Baznas Forge Strategic Collaboration to Advance Islamic Education</i>	<i>Collaboration in Islamic education</i>	<i>Islam as a solution for philanthropy and education</i>
22	Dari Tanah Wakaf hingga Layanan untuk Difabel: Dua Inovasi Kemenag Tembus Finalis Nasional, Sekjen Beri Apresiasi (<u>Kementerian Agama</u>) <i>From Waqf Land to Disability Services: Two Innovations by the Ministry of Religious Affairs Reach National Finalist, Secretary-General Applauds</i>	<i>Disability services and waqf</i>	<i>Islam as an inclusive system</i>
23	Puasa Ayyamul Bidh Agustus 2025: Cek Jadwal Lengkap dan Keutamaannya! (<u>Rumah Zakat</u>) <i>Ayyamul Bidh Fasting August 2025: Check the Complete Schedule and Its Merits!</i>	<i>Education on voluntary worship</i>	<i>Internal spiritualization of Islam</i>
24	Ulama, Umat, dan Negara (<u>UIN Jakarta</u>) <i>Scholars, People, and the State</i>	<i>Religion-state relations</i>	<i>Moderate Islam in governance</i>

25	Menag: Lulusan Pesantren Dapat Diterima di Universitas Internasional, Berkarier di Bidang Eksakta (<u>Kementerian Agama</u>) <i>Minister of Religious Affairs: Islamic Boarding School Graduates Can Be Accepted into International Universities and Pursue Careers in Science</i>	<i>Affirmation of Islamic boarding schools</i>	<i>Integration of Islamic knowledge and science</i>
26	Menag: Lulusan Pesantren Dapat Diterima di Universitas Internasional, Berkarier di Bidang Eksakta (<u>HIMPUH</u>) <i>Minister of Religious Affairs: Islamic Boarding School Graduates Can Be Accepted into International Universities and Pursue Careers in Science</i>	<i>Protection of congregational rights</i>	<i>Sharia as a norm of justice</i>
27	Doa Setelah Shalat Dhuha: Lengkap Arab, Latin, dan Artinya (<u>Rumah Zakat</u>) <i>Supplication After Dhuha Prayer: Complete in Arabic, Latin, and Its Meaning</i>	<i>Religious literacy</i>	<i>Rituals as reinforcement of faith</i>
28	Takdir Tak Selalu Indah, Tapi Selalu Mengandung Hikmah (<u>Rumah Zakat</u>) <i>Destiny Is Not Always Pleasant, but Always Contains Wisdom</i>	<i>Psychological support</i>	<i>Islamic theology of wisdom</i>
29	Takdir Tak Selalu Indah, Tapi Selalu Mengandung Hikmah (<u>Muhammadiyah</u>) <i>Destiny Is Not Always Pleasant, but Always Contains Wisdom</i>	<i>Community economy</i>	<i>Islam as an economic force</i>
30	Kemenag Dorong Wakaf Produktif sebagai Penggerak Pemberdayaan Umat (<u>Kementerian Agama RI</u>) <i>Ministry of Religious Affairs Encourages Productive Waqf as a Driver of Community Empowerment</i>	<i>Community empowerment</i>	<i>Waqf as a sharia-based economic strategy</i>
31	Syafiq Mughni: KHGT Hasil Ijtihad Muhammadiyah untuk Menyatukan Persaudaraan Islam se-Dunia (<u>Muhammadiyah</u>) <i>Syafiq Mughni: KHGT as Muhammadiyah's Ijtihad to Unite Global Islamic Brotherhood</i>	<i>Global brotherhood</i>	<i>Islamic cosmopolitanism</i>

From Table 3, the social and ideological embeddedness of Islamic discourse in news representation point to a variety of representations that construct Islam, not just as a ritual practice, but also as a social, economic, political and cultural feature. Ideological operations are not only conveyed in the representation of Islam as an act of charity, a comprehensive means of understanding, a faith reinforcement, an alignment between science and religion, a normative ethos of good and

cosmopolitan world view to legitimize Islam and extend the moral authority of Islam in the public realm. The results, therefore, show a close connection between social functions as praxis and ideological functions as normative constructions, construing Islam as both a meaningful and regulative factor in society today.

Discussion

Discourse Strategies in Islamic News Coverage

The strategies of Islamic news coverage that combine personalization, legitimization, interpellation, and moral imperatives have proven effective in facilitating internalization of religious values at a personal level while simultaneously encouraging readers' moral reflection. Key point/news hooks: The use of moral rhetoric and strategic framing in news coverage messages or press releases by politically active American Muslim organizations that prime individual freedoms (e.g., rights) and public actions (e.g., expressive behavior and protests) with strong moral language messages and themes appears to bolster message legitimacy and boost greater civic engagement (Bowe et al., 2021).

The legitimization strategy in religious and political discourse is typically achieved through the phenomenon of authorization, moralization, and rationalization, in order to validate a particular course of action or position, whether within the religious or political formation (Osisanwo, 2024). Thus, the combination of personalization, legitimization, interpellation, and moral imperatives in Islamic news coverage not only reinforces the personal internalization of religious values but also encourages moral reflection and social action.

In the digital context of Google News Indonesia, these discourse strategies are not limited to linguistic forms but are also embedded in the platform's technical architecture. Other strategies are manifested through emotive approaches, religious narratives, didactic-imperative forms, and interactive-functional expressions. Islam also stresses emphasis on interfaith dialogue, tolerance, and diversity integration as evident in the Qur'an, Hadith, and historical traditions, which promote peaceful coexistence in plural societies. Furthermore, Islamic education has a substantial impact towards the cultivation of the spiritual and global identity, self-reflection, self-awareness and the acceptance of diversity among the Muslim community and beyond (Saada, 2023). Maqasid al-Shari'ah and economic justice as a principle of social welfare and sustainable peace by reconciling between individual rights and wealth distribution.

In addition, within the context of 12-step recovery groups, piety is also seen as a process of taking on and remaking the systems of attention to the divine in a way that people create an engendered and emplaced piety agendas, both individually and collectively. global media trends that often dehumanize Islam through the binary of "us" versus "them," the representation found in Google News Indonesia humanizes Islam by situating it within everyday moral, social, and humanitarian contexts. Through value-oriented reporting and moral personalization, Islam is portrayed as empathetic, inclusive, and socially responsive—"close to the people," and even to the vulnerable or marginalized—thereby reinforcing its role as an agent of social change rather than a source of division. This framing provides a practical contribution to digital journalism and religious

communication: it exemplifies how Islamic discourse can be contextualized and humanized to foster public empathy, civic participation, and intercultural understanding.

Islamic Representations by the Media

Studies show that media representations of Islam are multifaceted, encompassing ritual, moral, cultural, and sociopolitical dimensions that continually evolve across contexts. Yet Islam and Muslims are often portrayed through stigmatizing labels—such as threats linked to terrorism and immigration—which reinforces the “Other” and fuels Islamophobia. The media also frequently conflates Islam as a religion with Islamism as a political movement, producing additional public confusion and discrimination (McGarry et al., 2023).

While stereotyping is widespread, representations remain diverse and sometimes contradictory. Social media occasionally depicts Islam as liberal and humanitarian, yet negative portrayals—associating it with extremism, terrorism, or gender discrimination—remain dominant.

Discursive Ideological Functions of Islamic Discourse in Google News Media

The mediation of Islam in the media fulfils social functions such as educational cooperation, religious literacy, endorsement of Islamic boarding schools, community strengthening, and global solidarity. Digital media helps reinvigorate collective identity, expand da'wah, and support educational collaboration and community empowerment, as seen in Indonesian Islamic institutions using social media to affirm identity and values (Kerim et al., 2025). Media likewise becomes a site of ideological contestation, where scholars and digital influencers construct inclusive narratives and foster transnational solidarity. Although portrayals of Muslims may enhance cohesion and understanding, they remain vulnerable to unethical and exclusivist manipulation.

Islamic ideology appears through philanthropy, integrative knowledge, justice-oriented values, and cosmopolitan principles that reinforce its moral legitimacy. Globally, Islam can operate as a diplomatic and branding instrument, exemplified by the UAE’s promotion of “moderate Islam” to strengthen its geopolitical standing. In the context of Google News aggregation, these ideological functions are also discursively shaped through digital mediation. Islamic discourse appears not only as a moral and spiritual framework but as a progressive ideology that integrates faith with knowledge, science, and global citizenship. Headlines and excerpts often emphasise inclusivism, interreligious tolerance, and cosmopolitan ethics—framing Islam as compatible with modernisation and scientific rationality (Prayitno et al., 2022; Sutarja et al., 2024). Such representations serve to challenge the monolithic stereotypes of Islam by projecting a constructive, future-oriented religiosity that aligns with global ethical discourses. The positive ideological functions reflected in Table 3—such as integration of science and religion, cosmopolitanism, and inclusiveness—illustrate how digital news coverage constructs Islam as both spiritually authentic and socially transformative.

This reinforces the notion that Islamic ideology in digital media operates as both a spiritual and sociopolitical force—bridging moral universality and contemporary global concerns, including peacebuilding, equality, and sustainable coexistence. In summary, the discourse strategies observed in Google News Indonesia demonstrate how Islamic media narratives can operate as

counter-hegemonic forces within the digital public sphere. By reversing the dominant Western framing that positions Islam within a “threat” or “security” paradigm, Google News Indonesia inclusive and value-oriented reporting articulates a counter-discourse of moral solidarity, social justice, and civic harmony. This suggests that Indonesian digital media not only reproduce theological meanings but also reshape global perceptions of Islam through a localized praxis of digital religiosity that bridges faith, ethics, and social transformation.

Conclusion

The representation of Islam in Google News Indonesia shows that Islamic ways of life retain social significance across personal, communal, and institutional spheres. Islam appears through spiritual teachings, value-based education, Qur’anic traditions, and state-backed moderation efforts. These texts represent socialised religious identity, reinforce moral norms, and support social cohesion.

Discursively, Islam is framed not only as a doctrine system but also as a humanist, activist, and problem-solving framework—positioned to address contemporary issues and strengthen multicultural harmony. Islamic discourse on Google News Indonesia thus serves as a contextually relevant and adaptable value system, acting as both a social mechanism and an ideological resource that promotes inclusive, solution-oriented perspectives.

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